

Research Commentary Article

Critical Conversations of Engaging with the AMTE Standards

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ABSTRACT: This article is based on an opening plenary session at the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators (AMTE) 2024 conference in Orlando, Florida, USA. The authors, who delivered the plenary in a panel format, focus specifically on the AMTE standard indicator that addresses *power and privilege*. This article is the product of the five authors reflecting on their panel and discussing its contents—in the form of this manuscript—with an external Open Reviewer. The result is a “quintalog” of the five authors in critical conversation with each other about their own reflections on the ways in which mathematics teacher educators and the AMTE standards engage with power and privilege—particularly in the midst of the current American (and, further, Floridian) political situation.

KEYWORDS: *teacher education, standards, power and privilege, critique*

In this article we share a written form of the opening session we presented at the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators (AMTE) 2024 Conference in Orlando, Florida, titled “Critical Conversations: AMTE Standards for Preparing Teachers of Mathematics in Social and Political Contexts.” Our goal for the opening session was to set the tone for the conference and have

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participants engage with five focal questions posed throughout the opening session regarding the AMTE standards. The description of the opening session panel was as follows:

Much has happened in the world and in mathematics education since the 2017 release of the Standards for Preparing Teachers of Mathematics. How do we (and how might we) leverage these standards to advocate for teachers, teacher educators, practices, programs, and policies at local, state, and national levels? What is missing in these standards that could help us better prepare teachers? How do or how should social and political issues impact what we do in mathematics teacher education? In this session, panelists will address these questions and engage the audience in conversations intended to promote critical consciousness with ourselves and with the teachers of mathematics that we prepare.

Specifically, we focused on the AMTE standard indicator, C.4.4, which addresses power and privilege. The standard is labeled “Understand Power and Privilege in the History of Mathematics Education” and includes the following descriptor: “Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics understand the roles of power, privilege, and oppression in the history of mathematics education and are equipped to question existing educational systems that produce inequitable learning experiences and outcomes for students” (AMTE, 2017).

It was important for the panelists to engage the audience in conversation about power and privilege as part of our panel because the conference was being held in Florida. Due to longstanding and recent political decisions made in the state of Florida in particular, attending this conference was not safe for many of our mathematics teacher educator (MTE) colleagues. Florida had passed harmful anti-trans/LGBTQIA+ laws at that time. The NAACP (National Association for the Advancement of Colored People) among other institutions had issued a travel advisory. As such, each panelist had to decide whether attending the conference aligned with our beliefs, which support that only a conference that is safe for all to attend is a conference that should be planned. Some of our colleagues chose not to attend this meeting (and we fully support that decision and also wrestled with that decision ourselves). Each of us incorporated a rationale for whether we decided to attend the conference and why we accepted the invitation to speak on the opening panel into our portion of the presentation as it explicitly addresses Power and Privilege in our community.

We write this paper with the idea of questioning systems via use of the standards. Instead of sharing a presentation where we talked for most of the time we selected to engage the audience with five questions. We contextualized each question and then allowed the audience to engage. We preview the questions here and present them again later to structure the paper.

- 1) What do you know about Standard Indicator C.4.4?
- 2) What is your history with the standards?
- 3) How prepared do you feel discussing issues of power, privilege, and oppression with the pre- or in-service teachers you work with?
- 4) When discussing issues of power, privilege, and oppression, how do you mitigate and respond to pushback?
- 5) How do you use the standards to advocate and educate?

Since our backgrounds and experiences varied widely we decided that each of us would introduce ourselves and then contextualize and respond to one of the questions. In our meetings leading up to the opening session Eva asked each panel member to share why they agreed to be on this panel. We also explicitly discussed how each of us came to decide on whether to travel to AMTE in

Florida in 2024. With transparency and humility, we openly share these viewpoints in each of our respective sections.

Opening: What Do You Know About Standard Indicator C 4.4?

(Written by Eva Thanheiser)

In this section, I first describe my decision to participate in the panel and attend AMTE. I then provide more detail about the author team and then discuss my understandings of Standard Indicator C 4.4.

My Decision to Participate in the Panel and Attend AMTE

I, Eva, considered carefully that both attending and not attending make statements. Two options seemed available to me: 1) don't attend the conference and thus don't financially support Florida or 2) attend and take a vocal stand. Some of the reasons I struggled were the anti-trans and anti-LGBTQIA+ legislation as well as the racial profiling, unjust detention, and deportations that were happening. Several groups, including the NAACP, issued travel advisories. It was a very hard decision for me. I was trying to figure out how to take a stand. I eventually decided to attend and advocate while at the conference.

I will examine three topics here (see Figure 1) that played into my decision to participate in the panel and attend the conference: politics, safety, and taking a stand. In terms of politics I disagree with a lot that is happening in Florida, in terms of safety I felt that it was reasonably safe for me to attend and then advocate which I did in part by wearing a bright yellow T-shirt that says "Say gay all day." Each panel member also selected to wear something to show visible support for minoritized folk in Florida. In the opening session, I invited audience members to come talk to me during the conference (and I invite you to email me when reading this paper) if they would like to chat.

Figure 1. Eva's slide displaying tensions about traveling to Florida.

The Author Team

Our author team came with a variety of experiences with the standards and as such was able to provide a varied experience with them. Jenny Bay-Williams was a member of the original author team that composed the first draft of the standards in 2015-2017. She brought a historical perspective which she lays out in her section below and thus we asked audience members to reflect on “What is your history with the standards?” Richard Velasco focused on the importance of doing critical self-reflection and shared his own story engaging with the standards. The question he posed was “How prepared do you feel to consider power and oppression?” Liza Bondurant addressed incorporating content and context and her question is “How do you mitigate and respond to pushback?” Yvonne Lai honed in on listening to each other and engaging and her question was “How do you use the standards to advocate and educate?” In Table 1 we lay out an overview of the *Standards and Related Indicators for Well-Prepared Beginning Teachers of Mathematics*.

Standard	Related Indicators
<u>C.1. Mathematics Concepts, Practices, and Curriculum</u>	
Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics possess robust knowledge of mathematical and statistical concepts that underlie what they encounter in teaching. They engage in appropriate mathematical and statistical practices and support their students in doing the same. They can read, analyze, and discuss curriculum, assessment, and standards documents as well as students’ mathematical productions.	C.1.1. Know Relevant Mathematical Content C.1.2. Demonstrate Mathematical Practices and Processes C.1.3. Exhibit Productive Mathematical Dispositions C.1.4. Analyze the Mathematical Content of Curriculum C.1.5. Analyze Mathematical Thinking C.1.6. Use Mathematical Tools and Technology
<u>C.2. Pedagogical Knowledge and Practices for Teaching Mathematics</u>	
Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics have foundations of pedagogical knowledge, effective and equitable mathematics teaching practices, and positive and productive dispositions toward teaching mathematics to support students’ sense-making, understanding, and reasoning.	C.2.1. Promote Equitable Teaching C.2.2. Plan for Effective Instruction C.2.3. Implement Effective Instruction C.2.4. Analyze Teaching Practice C.2.5. Enhance Teaching Through Collaboration With Colleagues, Families, and Community Members
<u>C.3. Students as Learners of Mathematics</u>	
Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics have foundational understandings of students’ mathematical knowledge, skills, and dispositions. They also know how these understandings can contribute to effective teaching and are committed to expanding and deepening their knowledge of students as learners of mathematics.	C.3.1. Anticipate and Attend to Students’ Thinking About Mathematics Content C.3.2. Understand and Recognize Students’ Engagement in Mathematical Practices C.3.3. Anticipate and Attend to Students’ Mathematical Dispositions
<u>C.4. Social Contexts of Mathematics Teaching and Learning</u>	
Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics realize that the social, historical, and institutional contexts of mathematics affect teaching and learning and know about and are committed to their critical roles as advocates for each and every student.	C.4.1. Provide Access and Advancement C.4.2. Cultivate Positive Mathematical Identities C.4.3. Draw on Students’ Mathematical Strengths C.4.4. Understand Power and Privilege in the History of Mathematics Education C.4.5. Enact Ethical Practice for Advocacy

Table 1. *Standards and Related Indicators for Well-Prepared Beginning Teachers of Mathematics.*

Responding to the Question: What Do You Know About Standard Indicator C 4.4?

I personally had not had much experience with the standards even though I am a longstanding and active member of the AMTE community. As such we figured that many people in the audience would need some time to respond to this question and make themselves familiar with the standard. In addition we thought this could be a good question to allow people to get to know one another as well. Thus we allowed some time to interact with each other about this standard in particular or about the standards in general.

What is Your History with AMTE and the AMTE Standards?

(Written by Jennifer Bay-Williams)

In this section I begin with how I became a part of AMTE and then I share the journey of history of the AMTE Standards, from the original inspiration, through the writing process, to the eventual implementation of the Standards and other related resources.

My Coming to Know AMTE

I joined AMTE as a doctoral student in the late 90s. Two years into my first job as an assistant professor, I was asked to run for secretary of this organization. With trepidation, I said yes. I was elected. I sat at my first board meeting in awe of all the activities that this organization was doing to support mathematics teacher education, while also surprised and excited that mathematics teacher educators of all levels of experience were energetically leading and participating in the organization. For me, AMTE has supported my own learning, facilitated most of my networking with other colleagues in the field, and grew my skills as a leader and a mathematics teacher educator. As the others on the panel, I had deep concerns about harmful anti-trans/LGBTQIA+ laws present in Florida and did not want my attendance to indicate anything else. I also have deep respect for AMTE, and consideration for how attendance (or lack thereof) can impact the organization. With this context in mind, I share my thoughts on the history of AMTE and the Standards for the Preparation of Teachers of Mathematics, for which I served as one of four lead writers.

My Panel Talk

Every document, certainly standards, reflect the time and space in which they are created. In an initial conversation with the panel, questions arose about the motivation and decisions made in the development of the AMTE Standards. We realized through months of conversation that (1) more mathematics teacher educators in the United States are aware of injustices toward some groups and (2) the Standards offer more than teacher educators may be aware of, and that could be used to advocate for more equitable teacher preparation. Jennifer's slide illustrates the Standards process, which serves as an advanced organizer for this section.

Article continues on the next page.

Figure 2. Jennifer's slide displaying the journey of the AMTE Standards for the Preparation of Teachers of Mathematics.

Inspiration

In February 2015, Nadine Bezuk, long-time Executive Director and Past President of AMTE was the individual selected for the esteemed Judith Jacobs lecture, a keynote session started at the AMTE conference in 2003 to challenge their colleagues on critical issues related to mathematics teacher education. Dr. Bezuk's talk (available on the AMTE website) asked 82 questions, including:

*What are we doing related to supporting teachers in developing their mathematics teaching?
Can we do more? Can we make a bigger, more systemic impact?
How can AMTE help?*

These questions were the *inspiration* for writing standards specific to preparing mathematics teachers. Within hours of this talk, AMTE leadership (the president and other board members) decided that AMTE standards, specifically focused on mathematics teacher preparation, could help the field. Shortly after the conference ended, the AMTE board invited four individuals to lead the work. Due to her talk and her extensive leadership and knowledge related to AMTE and mathematics teacher education in general, Nadine Bezuk was asked to lead the work. The board also invited three others to serve as lead writers, each focusing on a different grade-band. The resulting lead writer team was Doug Clements (early elementary), Nadine Bezuk (upper elementary), myself (middle school) and Gary Martin (high school). The lead writers collaborated with the AMTE board to invite an author team that would bring diverse perspectives, academic positions, and backgrounds. This included considerations of their grade-band expertise, research focus, geographic location, knowledge of accreditation and other standards, and whether they worked primarily in a College of Education or Mathematics Department. Listed here are the authors that accepted the invitation to serve on the AMTE standards writing team:

Julia Aguirre, University of Washington–Tacoma
Timothy Boerst, University of Michigan
Elizabeth A. Burroughs, Montana State University
Ed Dickey, University of South Carolina
Rochelle Gutiérrez, University of Illinois

Elizabeth Hughes, University of Northern Iowa
 DeAnn Huinker, University of Wisconsin–Milwaukee
 Karen Karp, Johns Hopkins University
 W. James Lewis, University of Nebraska
 Travis A. Olson, University of Nevada–Las Vegas
 Randolph Philipp, San Diego State University
 Nicole Rigelman, Portland State University
 Marilyn Strutchens, Auburn University
 Christine D. Thomas, Georgia State University, AMTE President
 Dorothy Y. White, University of Georgia

Aspiration

The writing team asked, “How would AMTE standards be different from other standards that describe expectations for the preparation of teachers, such as the Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation (CAEP) Standards?” We recognized that these other standards established the floor, and it was our charge to develop *Aspirational AND Attainable* standards. This phrase Aspirational AND Attainable was used regularly throughout our process. We captured this vision in the Introduction with the following five assumptions, the first assumption is particularly relevant to standard C.4:

- 1) Ensuring the success of each and every learner requires a deep, integrated focus on equity in every program that prepares teachers of mathematics.
- 2) Teaching mathematics effectively requires career-long learning.
- 3) Learning to teach mathematics requires a central focus on mathematics.
- 4) Multiple stakeholders must be responsible for and invested in preparing teachers of mathematics.
- 5) Those involved in mathematics teacher preparation must be committed to improving their effectiveness in preparing future teachers of mathematics.

Contemplation

The writing team first met in Las Vegas, sitting in a small room with tables arranged in one large square, to begin discussing what was most important for the initial preparation of teachers. Many ideas were added to chart paper that surrounded the room and deep discussion began about what was most important to keep and what may not be a priority for initial teacher preparation. In essence, the conversations focused on this essential question:

What is reasonable for a preservice teacher to know or be able to do (and what was not)? For some items on the wall, there was heated debate over the importance of the topic itself or whether that topic was more appropriate for advanced preparation. Some authors noted, “how can we expect _____ of preservice teachers when practicing mathematics teachers (and teacher educators) are themselves challenged to do well in that domain.” That day of discernment was a stand-out moment in my life as a mathematics teacher educator as I listened to Rochelle Gutiérrez articulately and passionately explain why we had to have what eventually became the C4 Standards. While a beginning mathematics teacher may not be able to advocate like an experienced teacher can, they must, “realize that the social, historical, and institutional contexts of mathematics affect teaching and learning and know about and are committed to their critical roles as advocates for each and every student” (AMTE Standard C4).

Another important contemplation over the early months of developing the standards was *who were these standards for?* We asked ourselves, are we focusing on those that teach mathematics in K-12? We worried that calling the standards, the Standards for the Preparation of Mathematics

Teachers, could lead to an interpretation that we were focusing on middle and high school teachers. The author team agreed that every educator in a position to teach mathematics, including early childhood and elementary teachers, special education teachers, and multilingual specialists have a significant impact on student learning of mathematics and thus these standards need to be written to attend inclusively to these educators. Thus the title, “Standards for the Preparation of Teachers of Mathematics” was adopted.

Construction

Writing took two years. And, not two years where you put down the work for a few months. The leads met every Tuesday for two hours. We met with our 4 Standards groups (I got to work with C4); we met with our grade band books (there is a chapter for every grade band- I led the middle school team). We moved into writing program standards. Drafts were reviewed by other organizations and individuals within AMTE. Revisions were made. Executive Summary written, etc., etc. The final resulting standards included 4 Candidate Standards (with 19 specific indicators) and 5 Program Standards (with 17 specific indicators). Candidate Standard 4 Social Contexts of Mathematics Teaching and Learning states:

Well-prepared beginning teachers of mathematics realize that the social, historical, and institutional contexts of mathematics affect teaching and learning and know about and are committed to their critical roles as advocates for each and every student.

Five of the 19 indicators are housed within this standard, acknowledging the critical importance of equity, access, and advancement in mathematics. These indicators are provided in Table 1.

Implementation

On February 7th, 2017, the Standards were released at the AMTE annual conference. The conference had a number of sessions focusing on the four candidate standards and there was significant conversation about using these standards in our programs. One common activity in the early years was for teacher educators or district leaders to self-assess the extent to which they were addressing the candidate standards and indicators (see Figure 3). In all such conversations (webinars and conference sessions), C.4 was identified as the standard that was lowest rated (meaning as educators, we had the most need to improve in that area). This was not a surprise as these standards at the time were the most specific guidance to date, on what a well prepared beginning teacher of mathematics might know and be able to do related to social contexts.

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AMTE Program Standards Self-Assessment				
Determine (and check the box) which rating best describes how prepared beginning teachers of mathematics are in your setting.				
N = Not doing this well! S = Satisfactory P = Promising W = Well-designed				
P.1 Partnerships. An effective mathematics teacher preparation program has significant input and participation from all appropriate stakeholders.				
P.1.1 Engage all partners productively. An effective teacher preparation program...	N	S	P	W
P.1.2 Provide Institutional Support	N	S	P	W
P.2 Pedagogical Knowledge and Practices for Teaching Mathematics				
P.2.1 Attend to Mathematics Content Relevant to Teaching	N	S	P	W
P.2.2 Build Mathematical Practices and Processes	N	S	P	W
P.2.3 Provide Sustained, Quality Experiences	N	S	P	W
P.3 Students as Learners of Mathematics				
P.3.1 Address Deep and Meaningful Mathematics Content Knowledge	N	S	P	W
P.3.2 Provide Foundations of Knowledge About Students as Mathematics Learners	N	S	P	W
P.3.3 Address the Social Contexts of Teaching and Learning	N	S	P	W
P.3.4 Incorporate Practice-Based Experiences	N	S	P	W
P.3.5 Provide Effective Mathematics Methods Instructors	N	S	P	W
P.4 Social Contexts of Mathematics Teaching and Learning				
P.4.1 Collaboratively Develop and Enact Clinical Experiences	N	S	P	W
P.4.2 Sequence School-Based Experiences	N	S	P	W
P.4.3 Provide Teaching Experiences with Diverse Learners	N	S	P	W
P.4.4 Recruit and Support Qualified Mentor Teachers and Supervisors	N	S	P	W
P.5 Recruitment and Retention of Teacher Candidates				
P.5.1 Recruit Strong Candidates	N	S	P	W
P.5.2 Address Diverse Community Needs	N	S	P	W
P.5.3 Provide Experiences and Support Structures	N	S	P	W

Figure 3. Program Self-Assessment Related to AMTE Standards.

As an organization, AMTE supported the creation of over a dozen [supplemental resources](#) to assist in implementing the Standards. In Kentucky (KAMTE – the AMTE affiliate) had retreats to dig into these standards. This led to various efforts, including the Math Identity working group – we contributed to the AMTE supplemental resources and we now have teacher educators from many states interested in collaborating to improve our attention to standard C.4.2 in our work!

These AMTE Standards for the Preparation of Teachers of Mathematics have been widely shared, are often included in syllabi, and were instrumental in the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) development of the Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation (CAEP) Special Program Area (SPA) standards for mathematics (NCTM, 2020). Yet, the extent that they have been implemented in any state or at any institution likely varies from “not at all” to “framing the entire program.”

In Summary

At the time that we wrote standard C4, these expectations were considered more robust and well-defined than anything that pre-dated it (including *Principles to Actions*, NCTM, 2014). Yet the world continues to change and that means the expectations for the preparation of teachers of mathematics must continue to evolve. Nadine Bezuk’s questions *still* apply for whatever comes

next in term of AMTE Standards and related actions: *Can we do more? Can we make a bigger, more systemic impact? How can AMTE help?*

How Prepared Do You Feel Discussing Issues of Power, Privilege, and Oppression with Your Students?

(Written by Richard Velasco)

In this section, I first provide some background and context about my relationship with AMTE as an organization. I then share what I presented during the conference.

My Coming to Know AMTE

I first signed up for membership with AMTE in May 2021 and submitted my first AMTE conference proposal for the 2022 annual conference in Henderson, Nevada. I was excited at the prospect of being a first-time attendee and presenter when I found out my proposal was accepted later that August. The COVID-19 pandemic, of course, was (and is) still ongoing, but we were at a point in that particular viral wave where more people had gotten the COVID-19 vaccine and the number of infections and death cases were declining. Thus, this particular annual conference was AMTE's first one back in person since the pandemic began in 2020. Perhaps it was stay-at-home fatigue, or perhaps it was not being able to experience in-person conferences since finishing my doctoral degree as a "pandemic graduate," but I was eagerly looking forward to attending the conference in person and networking with other math teacher educators in our field.

When the annual conference arrived in February 2022, I felt there was a bit of a cautious return to in-person conferencing. Organizers of the conference rightfully sent out caution statements about the ongoing pandemic, mandated face masks for all attendees of the conference, and also provided hybrid options for those who chose not to attend in person because of COVID-19. In addition to a nametag that labeled me as a first-time attendee, my inexperience at this conference was apparent—I did not know anyone and kept mostly to myself. I recognized some high-profile scholars and was also finally able to put names with faces (sort of, because of face masks) when I looked at the nametags, but it was obvious that everyone was still trying to navigate a "new normal" of conferencing during a global pandemic. I liked that the conference organizers provided name tag stickers, though, to help attendees nonverbally communicate their comfort level in being. A red sticker meant no physical contact during a greeting, a yellow sticker meant a handshake or a side hug, while a green sticker was the "okay" for a full-on hug. Still, at least from my perspective of never attending any prior AMTE annual conference, the return to an in-person meeting seemed fairly smooth and successful.

My first AMTE conference was a memorable one—I attended a couple of great sessions, had a successful session of my own, and made many new connections with colleagues from other institutions. I enjoyed it so much that I remember telling a colleague, "This is a conference I can see myself attending consistently." I was also in a time of professional transition during the AMTE 2022 annual conference, having just accepted a tenure-track faculty position at my current institution while finishing the last semester at my previous one. Thus, I attended and left the conference filled with so much joy and excitement and with my sights toward the next chapter of my career.

Fast forward to a year later, I became a member of AMTE's membership committee, attended and presented at the 2023 conference in New Orleans, Louisiana, and later was asked to be an opening session panelist for the 2024 conference in Orlando, Florida. I felt both honored and confused about why I was asked to be on the panel, mainly because I felt like I was still in the very nascent stages of navigating my identity as a math teacher educator and scholar and that I had not

contributed very much to the field. I was eventually told that the subject of the panel session was going to be about the AMTE standards and that they were looking for a panelist who was at the early-career stage of their career and who was working in a state with laws that were anti-CRT (critical race theory) and/or anti-DEI (diversity, equity, and inclusion). I took some time to think about participating on the panel and eventually agreed, considering the implications it would have for my career.

However, what I did not carefully consider were the harmful anti-trans/LGBTQIA+ laws present in Florida where the conference was going to be held. Many of my friends and colleagues, especially those who identified as queer, had already committed to not attending the conference in Orlando, mainly because of these harmful laws. I was told that it was too late to find a new city to host the conference as doing so would completely bankrupt the organization, so that was certainly not an option. I was also confused as to why there was not a hybrid option made available, especially for presenters, and especially because it had been done successfully the past couple of years (in fact, the 2023 opening session had a couple of panelists present virtually). From what I gathered based on a statement released from the organization, there were many obstacles involved in providing such a modality, which was still unclear and upsetting to me. Thus, I was conflicted about whether or not I should attend, and I felt guilty for even having such an internal conflict. Especially as someone who identifies as queer, I thought to myself, “Would it be hypocritical of me to attend and participate in this conference?” and “Why should I go and support a place that is harmful to a community I am a part of?”

Ultimately, I decided not to attend the AMTE 2024 annual conference in Orlando. I told the organizers and co-presenters that I would only participate in the panel if I could do so at a distance, but resolved within myself that I would not be at the conference physically. The organizers and my co-presenters were amenable to my request and provided the option for me to present virtually. However, that decision was very difficult to make. I am intentional yet cautious in using the phrase, “very difficult,” in describing my decision because I harbored a lot of internal conflict and constantly sat in deep tension about the costs of attending or not attending the conference. So much so that I started to even question my own integrity and wondered how I could not make such an easy decision as others did. “Am I the only one struggling through this decision?” “What sort of backlash will I go through if I go or not go?” “Why can’t the conference organizers make accommodations for their members to attend the conference at a distance?” These were just a few of the questions I was ruminating over leading up to the conference. To say that it was merely a notion of “internal conflict” is an understatement. The tensions brought me anxiety and it started to affect me emotionally and even subconsciously—I started to have dreams about scenarios of what would happen if I attended the conference in person or not. It was making me sick.

In the end, I was able to seek advice from a couple of scholars who I consider to be mentors. What they shared with me brought clarity and peace in my decision, which I did not have for some time since being asked to be a part of the panel. While I do not intend to disclose all that my mentors shared with me, a couple of pieces of advice that stood out to me, in particular, were the following: “There will be lots of opportunities like this in your career—go with what you feels right to do at this moment in time,” and “Others similar in your position and who may also be going through the same conflict will take notice and bring them peace and feelings of solidarity in their decision.” So, I came to my decision to not attend the 2024 annual conference out of solidarity—solidarity with the LGBTQIA+ community and solidarity with the allies who chose not to attend as a political statement of resistance. To me, this act of solidarity in not attending was more important in my mind and heart than what it would mean for my career. With that, I provide here in the following passages of this section what I shared during the opening panel session.

My Panel Talk

In my current position as an early-career assistant professor of math education, I have had the privilege of engaging with various critical scholars and educators in the field. Even then, I was reluctant to participate in the opening panel session due to a severe case of imposter syndrome. However, I eventually realized the value of sharing my journey and perspectives as a junior scholar and novice math teacher educator, especially in the context of the AMTE standards. Reflecting on my introduction to AMTE in 2022 and subsequent attendance at the 2023 annual conference and how little I knew about the standards, I recognized the importance of standards such as C.4.4., which addresses power dynamics in math education. Inspired by an anti-racist collaborative at my previous institution led by poet activist and literacy education scholar, Dr. Yolanda Sealey-Ruiz, I delved into her concept of "Archaeology of Self" (see Figure 4; Sealy-Ruiz, 2021, 2022) to address standard C.4.4, examining my own experiences with racism and oppression (Velasco, 2022). Engaging in an archaeology of self involves self-exploration, probing, and understanding of where issues of race, racism, and other forms of oppression live within us. It requires that teachers and we as teacher educators personalize racism and other forms of oppression and how it influences our pedagogy. This self-exploration has informed my approach to teacher education, where I openly discuss personal reflections with my math preservice teachers to foster critical dialogue and mathematical discourse. I advocate for the integration of discussions surrounding power, privilege, and oppression in math teacher education programs. I argue that for us to prepare prospective math teachers who “understand the roles of power, privilege, and oppression in the history of mathematics education and are equipped to question existing educational systems that produce inequitable learning experiences and outcomes for students,” it is necessary for teacher educators to embark on their own journey of self-preparation to effectively support prospective teachers in navigating these complex issues.

28th Annual CONFERENCE AMTE

Richard

“Teachers, face that teacher education programs do not prepare you for the moments we are living through in our society. Most do not provide access to the antiracist pedagogy needed for teachers to bear witness and act as change agents in our schools and society.” (Sealy-Ruiz, 2022, p. 25)

As math teacher educators, we must embark on our own journey of deep critical reflection before attempting to guide beginning teachers.

<https://shorturl.at/dnCU5>

Racial Literacy Development

Archaeology of Self

Interruption Interrupting racism and inequality at personal and systemic levels

Historical Literacy Develop a rich and contextual awareness of the historical forces that shape our communities and society

Critical Reflection Think through the various layers of our identities and how our privileged and marginalized status affect the work

Critical Humility Remain open to understanding the limits of our own worldviews and ideologies

Critical Love A profound ethical commitment to caring for the communities we live in

Deep excavation & exploration of beliefs, biases, and ideas... ...that shape how we engage in our work.

FIGURE 1
The six components of this racial literacy development model can guide language arts education. Image designed by Angel Acosta. Used with permission of Angel Acosta.

Figure 4. Richard’s slide displaying Archaeology of Self.

As I continue to navigate my role as an emerging MTE and scholar, I am continually reminded of the importance of ongoing self-reflection and growth. The journey of engaging in the "Archaeology of Self" has not only deepened my understanding of the complexities of power, privilege, and oppression but has also highlighted the need for humility and vulnerability in the

learning process. Openly sharing my own struggles and experiences with preservice teachers created a classroom environment where authenticity and empathy are valued. Through dialogue and collaborative inquiry, I encouraged students to critically examine their own beliefs and biases to help cultivate a sense of agency and responsibility in addressing inequities within the field of mathematics education. Moving forward, I envision a math teacher education program that fosters a sense of community among reflective practitioners who are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and dispositions to advocate for social justice and equity in their future math classrooms. I firmly believe that we as teacher educators first need to begin this process of preparation within ourselves, so that we may model such for our prospective teachers and go alongside this journey with them.

When Discussing Issues of Power, Privilege, and Oppression, How Do You Mitigate and Respond to Pushback?

(Written by Liza Bondurant)

Attending AMTE in Florida: A Conflict of Identity, Advocacy, and Privilege

In this section, I will provide my rationale for attending the AMTE conference. I genuinely appreciate the opportunity to join this conversation about the social, historical, and institutional contexts of mathematics education, and more specifically mathematics identity, because this is a topic near and dear to my heart and mind. Regarding my rationale for attending the conference in person, not a single cell in my heart or brain wanted to support the economy of Florida. The Florida government has passed oppressive laws that limit the freedom and protection of (1) educators, and (2) people in the LGBTQIA+ community, two markers of my identity and the identities of people I care radically about. I feel physically and emotionally ill each time I hear a report of a teacher losing their job because of what they say or the materials they use (Reich, 2023) or students in the LGBTQIA+ community experiencing anti-LGBTQIA+ victimization at school (Kosciw et al., 2022). After providing an overview of the toxic climate the Florida government has created I will return to identity because I see identity markers as a potential vehicle for solidarity and collective liberation.

Florida's laws oppress educators and people in the LGBTQIA+ community (GLSEN, 2024; Kosciw et al., 2022; Movement Advancement Project, 2024; National Education Association, 2023). For example,

- 1) HB-1557, the "Parental Rights in Education Act," commonly referred to as the "Don't Say Gay Bill" prohibits classroom instruction on sexual orientation or gender identity from kindergarten through 3rd grade, and requires age-appropriate instruction thereafter.
- 2) HB-7, the "Individual Freedoms Act," commonly referred to as the "Stop Woke Act" amends Florida's non-discrimination statute to prohibit educational institutions from compelling students or employees to accept certain specified concepts related to race, color, sex, or national origin in training or instruction, but it does allow these topics to be discussed objectively without endorsement.
- 3) HB-1467, the "Curriculum Transparency Bill" requires school districts to ensure transparency in selecting instructional materials.

Through vague legislation about controversial topics, such as teaching about race, racism, American history, sexuality, and gender, Florida and other states have created a climate of fear among educators (Galluscio, 2023). The number of book bans across the U.S. continues to grow, and the climate in Mississippi, where I live and work, is similar to that of Florida (PEN America,

beliefs, and positionalities (Johnson & Fonbuena, 2023). Self-study and action research—what some refer to as "me-search," or research connected to one's identity or context (Gardner et al., 2017)—are essential first steps. Each of my co-authors and I have engaged in this process, using our own experiences to inform our understanding of the standards. By starting with ourselves, we build a foundation of authenticity and integrity. This approach also helps me lead by example when working with teachers, making them more receptive and reducing resistance. Therefore, this is one way to avoid pushback. It's through this ongoing cycle of self-reflection, action, and sharing that we not only practice what we preach but also continue to grow and learn alongside others.

I believe as MTEs, we must move beyond focusing solely on content to foreground equity in all aspects of our work. In my early years, I approached the standards in the order they were presented, placing content first and equity later. However, in hindsight, I realize that equity cannot be treated as an add-on or secondary consideration. It must be foundational and at the forefront of our efforts. Now, as I reflect on my work through the lens of Indicator C.4.4, I see how centering equity from the start is essential for creating meaningful, transformative change in mathematics education.

Doing the work outlined in Indicator C.4.4 can be intimidating, especially in the current political and social climate. Felton-Koestler & Koestler, (2017) grapple with the question of whether the work of MTEs can be politically neutral. Kung (2024) highlights how mathematics educators recognize inequities, yet laws and policies make addressing them difficult. The media and legislative actions often amplify fear. In these ways, laws, policies, and the media are a form of pushback MTEs must face. Since 2023, 82 Anti-Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) laws have been proposed across 28 states and the U.S. Congress, targeting DEI initiatives in education (The Chronicle of Higher Education, 2024). These laws limit discussions about race, gender, and identity in classrooms, creating a climate of fear that can lead to self-censorship. So far, 13 of these laws have passed, 12 have been enacted, and others are still being debated (The Chronicle of Higher Education, 2024). Anti-DEI laws refer to legislation designed to restrict DEI-related programs or content, similar to how other initiatives, such as the American Civil Liberties Union's (2024) tracking of attacks on LGBTQIA+ rights, monitor laws that limit civil rights. This political context matters, as it cultivates fear among educators and perpetuates oppression. In this climate, I believe we must remember that fear is often the heartbeat of such oppressive systems. MTEs can respond to the pushback from laws, policies, and the media by being informed about the accurate specific details of the laws and policies, organizing with like-minded people, clarifying misinformation about laws and policies, and advocating for change in unjust laws and policies.

Racism is a form of systemic oppression, and neutrality in the face of it is not an option. Tatum (1997) uses the metaphor of a moving walkway to illustrate the choices we have regarding racism. The walkway represents the structural advantages that benefit those with the powerful or privileged identity markers. Racists confidently walk forward, actively supporting and endorsing racism (e.g., members of White supremacist groups like the Ku Klux Klan or Proud Boys). Nonracists, while not actively promoting racism, remain passive by standing still on the walkway. Despite good intentions, this inaction, or neutral stance, contributes to the perpetuation of racist systems. Antiracists, on the other hand, turn around and walk in the opposite direction, actively challenging and working to dismantle these systems. They seek to understand how policies and practices uphold racism and collaborate with others to create change (Tatum, 1997). This metaphor highlights why we cannot remain neutral; a neutral stance is equivalent to being part of the problem. We must push against racism by taking an active stance, or we inadvertently allow its continuation.

I believe this analogy can be applied to other forms of systemic oppression. Mathematics educators have contributed to the unjust sorting and ranking of learners and mathematics learning spaces have created complacent and compliant citizenry for far too long. Mathematics educators possess a great deal of power. In our society success in mathematics is tied to power and privilege. Mathematics educators are gatekeepers and the curricular, instructional, and assessment decisions mathematics educators make have profound impacts on students' long-term trajectories. Through *creative insubordination*, we can not just *play the game*, but also *change the game*. According to Gutiérrez, creative insubordination is related to changing the game rather than just playing the game because it involves teachers actively working on the critical axis of identity and power, challenging and transforming dominant norms and practices in education that prioritize access and achievement at the expense of equity and social justice. By engaging in creative insubordination, educators seek to shift the focus from merely helping students succeed within existing structures to fundamentally altering those structures to better address issues of identity, power, and systemic inequities (Gutiérrez, 2002, 2009, 2018). As previously mentioned, we can find strength and support through working with a community of like-minded people.

The aspiring mathematics teachers I work with have generally responded positively to the activities I implement that align with Indicator C.4.4. However, as prospect theory suggests, negative responses or pushback, even if they come from only a few, tend to linger in our memories more than the positive ones (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). As a white, middle-class MTE, I am aware that some of my identity markers align with those of many of the teachers I work with, which may make it easier for me to navigate these conversations. Still, I have found that sharing my own experiences of power and privilege, along with stories of personal encounters with oppression, helps foster a sense of empathy and awareness among the teachers. These discussions help the teachers engage more deeply with forms of oppression they may not have personally experienced, while also challenging any resistance that may arise.

Looking at the *Intersectional Identities Wheel of Power* (Figure 5), we see many identity markers. I like how this wheel has continuums, not just dichotomies for each identity marker. I think that the wheel has the potential to serve as a tool for uniting people, including people who might pushback against discussing issues of power, privilege, and oppression. Most people identify with at least one traditionally marginalized identity marker. People with different marginalized identity markers can relate to each other based on their different, but similar experiences of oppression. For example, in my past experiences white teachers who identify as women have stated that they do not feel that racism is an issue anymore and claim that they treat all of their students the same. As white women, these teachers have not experienced racism, but as young women they have likely experienced sexism and ageism. I have used these oppressive experiences to talk to the teachers about the invisible structures and norms that uphold systems of oppression. By talking about the forms of oppression they have experienced, sexism and ageism, they have realized people who identify with other marginalized identity markers, such as people of color, also experience oppression.

While connecting through our marginalized identity markers can serve as a helpful entry-point for discussions, I caution the teachers I work with against falling into an "oppression Olympics" mindset, as the goal is not to compete over experiences of suffering. Oppression is detrimental, and all forms of suffering must be addressed and alleviated. I acknowledge that teachers may feel threatened by the idea that their students could be experiencing oppression in mathematics classrooms. To address this, I emphasize that harm in mathematical experiences often arises from the interactions among those co-constructing those experiences. Once we acknowledge this reality, we can shift our focus to facilitating healing from the trauma associated with mathematics learning.

In this regard, I believe a key area for growth in our profession lies in providing mental health training and services for both mathematics educators and students.

MTEs may encounter resistance or pushback when discussing power, privilege, and oppression. By beginning with me-search and discussing personal, social, and systemic levels of oppression involved in mathematics education I have been able to navigate these challenges. I believe that by advocating for equity, we can create environments where every individual can know, use, and enjoy mathematics.

How Do You Use the Standards to Advocate and Educate?

(Written by Yvonne Lai)

In this section, I begin by describing moments in my professional life that shaped my view of discourse in and about education, especially about the relationships between mathematics and education. Then, I share my panel remarks related to the need for mathematics teacher educators to work and learn both individually and in community. I suggest that advocating for ethical mathematics teacher education requires knowing how we hold power, and that the Standards can be used as a common text to educate ourselves on power in mathematics, teaching, and education.

When I was in graduate school in mathematics, now two decades ago, I remember hearing that work in mathematics education is only for mathematicians who don't make it. This myth is ugly in all its prejudice and baked with the animosity of the Math Wars of the 1990s-2000s. And now, though the mathematics research community as a whole is more inclusive to mathematics education and mathematics educators (as evidenced by collaborations such as Smith et al. (2021) and Sword et al. (2024)), there is still work to be done for mathematics educators and their work to be fully welcomed.

Years later, when I pursued mathematics education against a prevailing sentiment of losing status (what is status when you can't do the work you want to do?), I began attending AMTE conferences. Sometime in my first few years, in a lunch line, I heard three mathematics teacher educators expressing a desire that they "wish[ed] we could just tell mathematicians what to do." And so there is also work to be done for mathematics educators and mathematicians (however these are defined, and however mutually overlapping these identities may be) to genuinely see value in the perspectives and lived experiences of the other (yes, I use this term purposefully).

In mathematics education history, math wars (with a lowercase "m" and "w") come and go, though some quake more than others. We live in a moment now where we are feeling the ground move beneath us in ever-growing waves. There are heated political battles about what should be taught, how content is taught, and the resources and discourse that teachers can and should (not) use. Florida is a stark example, as Liza and Eva detailed. There are also fights across the country about mathematics content, standards, and instruction. Advocates fight proxy wars via X/Twitter, where it is all too easy to think that victory is a clever put-down.

All wars have costs, even discursive math wars. The cost comes in the form of loss of trust in professions and individual representatives of professions (such as mathematics or education), and in the loss of intellectual work that may have resulted if would-be-cooperators could have crossed boundaries to make a collaborative product that no one individual could have conceived. Mathematics teacher education is too complex—and too significant—for any one individual or profession to be able to make all the decisions.

What does this have to do with my decision to attend AMTE and speak on this panel? It is rare for someone who wrote a dissertation in mathematics, and who now does professional work in mathematics teacher education, to be showcased in an opening session. Yet if we are to make

progress on any of the problems that face us in *mathematics teacher education*, we will need perspectives from *mathematics*, *teaching*, and *education* (see Figure 6). More importantly, we need these perspectives to interact with each other, and for those with particular perspectives to co-learn from one another. These were some of my thoughts when I first received the invitation. And then, I found out that AMTE was to be held in Florida. Several colleagues of mine had already committed to not attending, for reasons similar to those that Liza and Eva described. At the same time, AMTE is a hub for mathematics teacher education, and I knew of other colleagues who would attend, including graduate students and early career faculty some of whom identify as or who have children who identify as LGBTQIA+. Conferences only function if enough people participate. Ultimately, I chose to attend. I attended to represent mathematicians-who-are-mathematics-educators (while recognizing that to view “mathematician” and “mathematics educator” as dichotomous is false and at the same time recognizing and respecting professional distinctiveness and qualities), and to be an ally for those whom Florida’s laws marginalize. I now share my panel remarks, where we as a group chose to highlight AMTE Standard C.4: Social Context of Mathematics Teaching and Learning.

Figure 6. Yvonne’s slide displaying bridging between mathematics, teaching, and education.

Panel Remarks

We live in a moment of unproductive debate and frustration. “Unproductive debate” means talking (or yelling) past each other, whether in writing or in speech. When this happens about something that is existentially important to us, we feel threatened.

For those of us who care deeply about mathematics, we may feel anxious for the future of mathematics. For those of us who want more children to flourish in the world, we may feel frightened for their chances to nurture mathematical literacy. Anxiety and fright make it hard to see clearly, to listen compassionately, and to find a way forward.

I am a mathematics teacher educator who works in a mathematics department. I am here because mathematics teacher education involves education, teachers, and mathematics, and I want to emphasize the importance of linking all three, and with the context and climate that surrounds us.

Richard and Liza have urged us to know ourselves. When we are Mathematics Teacher Educators, we work in *community*. Our community includes math departments, schools of education, school districts, and more. Not only do we need to know ourselves as *individuals*, but we need to know ourselves as a *community*. Whether we are in mathematics departments, schools of education, or a school district, we need to reach out to each other.

The theme of this opening session is a reflection on the AMTE Standards in the current political moment. I choose to begin my remarks with a characterization of the moment because the AMTE Standards present one possible context for reaching out. As Jenny stated, they represent a vision of where we want to go.

Let's take as an example Standard C.4: Social Context of Mathematics Teaching and Learning. To use this text as a shared platform, we need to know ourselves as a community and allow for co-constructing learning within community. Knowing ourselves as a community can begin by unpacking together some of the terms within the text of Standard C.4:

“Mathematical strength.”

“Access.”

“Power.”

“History of Mathematics Education.”

“Ethical.”

In any particular interaction, we do not have to have an exact precise notion for each. In fact, I would argue that we do not and we cannot. We all have different perspectives and experiences that we bring to bear on their meanings. But we need to be willing to learn from each other. The point is not agreement; the point is rethinking, listening, reflection, and learning. The point is asking questions to find common ground, even as we recognize that we launch from common ground in different directions.

Mathematical Strength

What would it take for us to recognize mathematical strength especially when it does not look like or feel like something we have thought about or experienced before? What would it take to name mathematical strength in all students, with a special awareness of students who may not look or act like us?

Access

What does it look like for all students and all teachers to have access to meaningful experiences with mathematics? A recent result suggests that even when teachers have increased traits thought to be predictive of good teaching, the instruction in the end may not be equitable teaching (Melhuish et al., 2022). As a community, we are still learning what it means to not only assign competence but also to create opportunities for all students to have their brilliance harnessed.

Power

What is power in the classrooms you have been in and what could holding power be? What would it take to teach and learn so that power can look like this? We must understand power, and how it is held because we are Mathematics Teacher Educators. Our notion of power includes who participates in our classrooms, who participates in future teachers' classrooms, and who participates in mathematics in society.

History of (Mathematics) Education

The Math Wars of the 1990s-2000s continue to have repercussions for our community, where mathematicians may feel excluded in “mathematics education” spaces, and mathematics educators

may feel excluded in “mathematics” spaces. Accusation and resentment do not lead to listening, let alone collaboration. We must recognize this history.

More gravely, in 1882, Congress passed the Chinese Exclusion Act. This act prohibited immigration from China for a decade and also prohibited any Chinese currently living in the US from becoming citizens. In 1885, California passed State Assembly Bill 268, which legalized separate schools for “Mongolian or Chinese” children. In the 1930s, a principal in Lemon Grove, CA, turned away Mexican children seeking to enter. In the wake of *Brown v. Board* in 1954, more than 35,000 Black teachers and administrators lost their jobs. Our lived experiences and perceptions today are inevitably shaped by those who came before us, and of the past events they lived. The effects of discrimination continue to impact visibility and longevity in the profession of teaching.

Ethical

As we consider these terms and their implications, we must ask: What does it mean to act ethically?

The standards represent one way to advocate and educate for equitable mathematics education and mathematics teacher education. As mathematics teacher educators, we have a responsibility to advocate for our students and our teachers. Doing so involves bringing to light our notions that bear on our power and how we hold it: mathematical brilliance, access to mathematics, history of mathematics and its education, and mathematical identity. These notions show up in the standards.

The standards are intended as common text to guide the vision and commitments for a community’s mathematics teacher education. When we in our own communities come to individual and collective understanding of how we each and together can and do hold mathematical power, we can then turn to how to design and enact our programs to nurture our students’ and teachers’ sense of identity and power.

Discussion

(Written by Eva Thanheiser)

We closed our session by opening up the floor to questions, insights, compliments, etc. In the ensuing discussion, several points were highlighted. First, there was an emphasis on the fact that the contributions of all panelists across their experiences were valuable (and we agree!). In fact, there was a discussion about how important it was to include researchers with varied experiences on the panel, especially junior faculty members. We all have much to learn from and with each other. Second, equity is central to all mathematics education. Mathematics and mathematics education are not and can never be neutral (Thanheiser, 2023), and as such power, privilege, and oppression must be considered in mathematics teacher education. Third, AMTE should listen to its members. Many of the AMTE members do not feel seen or heard by the leadership. This was particularly highlighted by the location of the 2024 conference in Florida combined with a focus on in-person attendance at that conference. The new board has lots of challenges in terms of healing and relational reparation from vulnerable members whose requests may have been ignored or felt neglected. We call on AMTE to acknowledge the pain and hurt that many members of AMTE went through for the organization’s decision to not, at the very least, provide hybrid options for members and presenters who did not feel safe to attend in person. Thus, we make the following suggestions for future AMTE conference planning committees: Consider state laws that would affect vulnerable members and stakeholders of AMTE. Release solidarity statements regarding resistance to harmful state laws where conferences may be held. Provide hybrid

attendance options. Listen to members' requests, especially from vulnerable populations and those who are most affected by the harmful laws imposed by states where the conference is held.

We came together on this panel and shared a powerful experience of opening up with each other and then the AMTE community on all the issues addressed above, supporting each other, and building a community. The audience engaged with us in the questions we posed and set the tone for the conference. Each of us had conversations following the session with attendees about the powerful experience of being part of such an opening discussion.

Afterword: The Open Review Process

One of the distinguishing characteristics of the Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education (JTM-ME) is the option of double-masked review or, alternatively, open review where authors and the reviewer openly engage with each other to improve the manuscript. Because our writing here drew on our identities in explicit ways, and a central theme is knowing ourselves individually and collaboratively, we elected for open review.

Dr. Courtney Koestler agreed to serve as our open reviewer. After reading our initial manuscript, they met with us to provide feedback that sharpened the form and substance of our writing. As part of this initial discussion, Courtney talked about the tensions of serving in the role of being an open reviewer (for the first time). They discussed feeling like they were serving both as a reviewer and a colleague/commenter. It was in that spirit that they offered critical feedback on the manuscript. We subsequently submitted a revision to them and the journal, and again received thoughtful feedback on structure and language. We are grateful to their time and insight in improving our work, and to the journal for offering this transformative process.

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